

The Kepler trochoid

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Kepler's description of planetary motion produced the famous transcendental equation

$$(KE) \quad M = E - e \sin(E)$$

connecting angular variables he termed 'anomalies' to the orbital eccentricity e [1]. The graphic below illustrates the geometry.

The location of a planet P on its elliptical path around the sun is defined by the pair (r, v) : the orbital radius r and the 'true anomaly' angle v .

The central angle E , termed 'eccentric anomaly', is related to the radius r , semi-major axis a , and elliptical eccentricity e as

$$(1) \quad r = a(1 - e \cos(E))$$

where the eccentricity is $e = (1 - (b^2/a^2))^{1/2}$

In turn, the two angles E and v are related to the semi-minor axis b and radius r as

$$(2) \quad v = \sin^{-1}((b/r) \sin(E))$$

The 'mean anomaly' $M = M(t)$ - an angular speed - is the only explicitly time-dependent variable:

$$M(t) = 2\pi t/T \quad T = \text{orbital period}$$

(KE) becomes important because solving for E is the key to providing a positional fix for the planet P in its ecliptic plane, once the angular speed M and the ellipse parameters (a, b) are known. Thus

$$E \Rightarrow (1) \quad r \Rightarrow (2) \quad v$$

Now, a conventional trochoid has the parametric representation [2]

$$x(t) = \alpha t - \beta \sin(t)$$

$$y(t) = \alpha - \beta \cos(t)$$

(KE) and the radial equation (1) look suspiciously close to a special trochoid: set

$$x = \mathbf{M}, \quad y = \mathbf{r/a}, \quad \alpha = 1, \quad \beta = \mathbf{e}$$

The Kepler trochoid (KT) is:

$$\text{(KE)} \quad \mathbf{M} = \mathbf{E} - \mathbf{e} \sin(\mathbf{E})$$

$$\text{(1)} \quad (\mathbf{r/a}) = \mathbf{1} - \mathbf{e} \cos(\mathbf{E})$$

where the eccentric anomaly \mathbf{E} becomes the independent variable. In Cartesian form the KT is [3]

$$\mathbf{r/a} + \mathbf{e} \cos\{\mathbf{M} + (2\mathbf{r/a} - (\mathbf{r/a})^2 - \mathbf{1} + \mathbf{e}^2)^{1/2}\} = \mathbf{1}$$

yet another transcendental equation, this time for the orbital radius \mathbf{r} , though constrained necessarily by a (real-valued) square-root term: $(\mathbf{r/a}) \geq \mathbf{1} - \mathbf{e}$.

Below are (KT) plots of one arch for Mars (in red), with $\mathbf{e} = 0.0934$, and Mercury (in black) which has with the highest eccentricity of all solar planets, $\mathbf{e} = 0.2056$.

For eccentric anomalies $\mathbf{E} = \pi/2$ and $\mathbf{E} = 3\pi/2$, the radius $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{a}$ irrespective of eccentricities, hence the intersections.

Finally, an easily solvable quadratic yields another expression for \mathbf{E} .

Clearly

$$((\mathbf{E} - \mathbf{M})/\mathbf{e})^2 + ((\mathbf{1} - (\mathbf{r/a}))/\mathbf{e})^2 = \mathbf{1}$$

leading to a quadratic whose positive solution is

$$\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{M} + (\mathbf{e}^2 - (\mathbf{1} - (\mathbf{r/a}))^2)^{1/2}$$

a re-casting of (KE) with the same constraints as above.

References

[1] P. Colwell, *Solving Kepler's Equation*, Willmann-Bell, 1993

[2] Wikipedia article on the trochoid

[3] A. Cusmariu, 'Cycloids old and new', <https://zenodo.org/records/13751134>